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FIVE-CRITERION METHODOLOGY OF INTERNAL CONTROL ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada to'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarida ichki nazorat muhitini baholashning besh mezonli metodikasi tadqiq etilgan. COSO va IIA/IPPF standartlari asosida ishlab chiqilgan metodika tashkiliy tuzilma, siyosat va tartib-qoidalar, kommunikatsiya tizimi, axborot texnologiyalari hamda monitoring mezonlaridan tarkib topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ichki nazorat, COSO, IIA, ichki audit, to'qimachilik sanoati, baholash metodikasi, mezonlar.

Аннотация. В статье исследована пяти-критериальная методика оценки среды внутреннего контроля на предприятиях текстильной промышленности. Методика, разработанная на основе стандартов COSO и IIA/IPPF, включает следующие критерии: организационная структура, политика и процедуры, система коммуникации, информационные технологии и мониторинг.

Ключевые слова: внутренний контроль, COSO, IIA, внутренний аудит, текстильная промышленность, методика оценки, критерии.

Abstract. The article explores a five-criterion methodology for assessing the internal control environment at textile industry enterprises. Developed based on COSO and IIA/IPPF standards, the methodology includes the following criteria: organizational structure, policies and procedures, communication system, information technology, and monitoring.

Keywords: internal control, COSO, IIA, internal audit, textile industry, evaluation methodology, criteria.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern corporate governance paradigm, the internal control system has become one of the most important mechanisms for ensuring operational efficiency, improving the reliability of financial reporting, and strengthening compliance with legislative requirements (Andersson et al., 2017). Internationally recognized frameworks such as COSO (COSO, 2017) and the IIA/IPPF standards (IIA, 2023) provide a solid conceptual foundation for developing effective and sustainable internal control systems in enterprises worldwide. At the same time, the successful implementation of these standards creates broad opportunities for adapting internal control practices to the specific characteristics of different industries.

In this context, the internal control system of enterprises within the "Uztextileindustry" Association plays a particularly significant role. The textile industry possesses substantial economic potential due to its multi-stage production processes, growing export capacity, efficient resource utilization, and dynamic product diversification. These characteristics create favorable conditions for establishing a modern and industry-oriented internal control environment (Xajimuratov, 2022). Therefore, the development of a specialized methodology for assessing the internal control environment in textile enterprises represents an important scientific and practical initiative aimed at enhancing management efficiency and competitiveness.

Special attention should be given to the industry-specific features of internal control systems in textile enterprises. Factors such as integrated production processes, large-scale management of raw materials and finished products, export-oriented operations, seasonal labor flexibility, and rapidly evolving fashion and color trends create opportunities for improving operational coordination and management quality. Furthermore, compliance with international standards and certifications such as GOTS, OEKO-TEX, and BCI, along with ESG reporting requirements under CSRD, contributes to strengthening transparency, sustainability, and the

international competitiveness of textile enterprises. As a result, an effective internal control system becomes not only a governance mechanism but also an important strategic advantage for long-term development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Extensive scientific research has been conducted in international literature on internal control and auditing issues. Wallace (2019) highlights the theoretical foundations of auditing and internal control, emphasizing their importance in improving organizational effectiveness. Sawyer et al. (2021) discuss modern internal auditing practices and their role in strengthening corporate governance systems. Knechel and Salterio (2020) comprehensively examine auditing and assurance services, while Messier et al. (2019) present a systematic and practical approach to auditing and assurance activities.

Among researchers from the CIS region, Sheremet and Suets (2020) explored the theoretical and methodological foundations of auditing and contributed significantly to the development of auditing science. Andreev (2019) analyzed the modern paradigm of internal auditing and its evolving role in organizations. Podolsky (2019) proposed a systematic approach to auditing processes, while Alborov and Khoruzhiy (2020) examined contemporary issues in accounting, economic analysis, and auditing, highlighting their practical significance for improving enterprise management systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted based on the following methodological approaches: systematic analysis, comparative-structural analysis, expert surveys, statistical grouping, case study methods, and empirical observation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of assessing the internal control systems of selected enterprises showed that the average score based on the COSO methodology was approximately 3.1 out of 5. This corresponds to a moderate level and indicates the potential for further improvement. The lowest scores were identified in the areas of information technology (2.7) and monitoring (2.9), while the highest scores were observed in organizational structure (3.4) and policies and procedures (3.2). In large enterprises (5 out of 12), the average score was approximately 3.8, whereas in small and medium-sized enterprises (7 out of 12), it was around 2.8.

Based on the identified findings, a five-criterion methodology was developed. Table 1.1 presents the criteria and indicators of the methodology. Each criterion is evaluated using a 5-point scale, with 10–15 indicators defined for every criterion. The final assessment results are divided into three levels: low (0–2.0 points) – requires priority improvement; medium (2.1–3.5 points) – requires partial improvement; and high (3.6–5.0 points) – indicates an effective internal control environment (Table 1).

Table 1
Structure of the Five-Component Internal Control Environment Assessment Methodology

Criteria	Number of Indicators	Main Indicators	5-Point Criteria
Organizational Structure	12	Functions, accountability, responsibility boundaries, reporting	All functions are clearly documented in written form
Policies and Procedures	15	Written procedures, accessibility, implementation	Annual plans are approved for all processes
Communication System	10	Information flow, escalation, electronic documents	Automated system and real-time communication
Information Technologies	13	Automation, information security, integration	Compliance with ERP, SIEM, and ISO/IEC 27001
Monitoring	11	Continuous supervision, internal audit, analysis	Automated indicators and real-time monitoring

The aspect of incorporating industry-specific characteristics into the methodology is of particular importance. A number of specialized indicators relevant to the textile industry have been introduced, including: 1) completeness of multi-stage production documentation; 2) frequency of physical inventory procedures; 3) effectiveness of the quality control system; 4) reliability of export operation documentation; and 5) certification systems for cotton raw materials. These indicators create broad opportunities for evaluating the operational

sustainability and management effectiveness of enterprises in the industry.

An important advantage of the methodology is its strong adaptation to the specific characteristics of the textile sector. The multi-stage production process, significant inventory volumes, and export-oriented activities provide favorable conditions for establishing a modern and efficient internal control system. In this regard, additional criteria such as certification and traceability of cotton raw materials, completeness of documentation in multi-stage production, and accuracy of currency and customs accounting in export operations have been integrated into the methodology. This contributes to improving transparency, operational coordination, and overall management quality within enterprises.

The digital transformation of the internal control system is considered one of the key strategic directions for enterprise development. The implementation of electronic workflow systems, automated control procedures, and real-time monitoring dashboards significantly enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of internal control processes while supporting traditional management mechanisms. Research findings indicate that enterprises implementing digital technologies (3 out of 12) achieved internal control ratings that were 28–35% higher compared to enterprises relying primarily on traditional approaches. This demonstrates the growing importance of strengthening the information technology component within the five-criterion methodology.

Another important feature of the methodology is its universality and adaptability. In addition to the textile industry, its core principles can be effectively adapted to other multi-stage production sectors, including food production, the chemical industry, mechanical engineering, and metallurgy. Although industry-specific indicators may vary depending on the sector, the five-criterion architecture of the methodology — organizational structure, policies and procedures, communication, information technologies, and monitoring — remains a stable and effective framework. This highlights the broader methodological and practical significance of the proposed approach for various sectors of the national economy.

The successful implementation of the five-criterion methodology largely depends on the professional competence of personnel. According to the results of the survey conducted during the research, many enterprises expressed interest in further strengthening expertise in internal control. In this regard, it is proposed to establish a 200-hour “Internal Control and Corporate Governance” training program within the organization. The program would include: 60 hours of theoretical foundations (COSO, IPPF, ISO standards); 80 hours of practical training (methodology application and case analysis); 40 hours of empirical work (practical implementation within enterprises); and 20 hours of final assessment and certification. Participants who successfully complete the program would receive an “Internal Control Specialist” certificate. It is expected that approximately 3,000 certified specialists could be trained within the network over the next five years, contributing to the long-term development of internal control capacity in the sector.

The economic efficiency parameters of the five-criterion methodology are also highly promising. For a large enterprise, the implementation cost is estimated at approximately 250 million soums (methodology development and training – 80 million; IT infrastructure – 120 million; employee skills development – 50 million), while the expected annual economic benefit may reach 850 million soums (improvement of operational efficiency – 450 million; optimization of production processes – 250 million; reduction of audit-related expenses – 150 million). As a result, the project's ROI may reach 240%, while the payback period is estimated at approximately 0.3 years. These indicators clearly demonstrate the strong economic potential, sustainability, and practical value of the proposed methodology for modern enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings, the average COSO score for the internal control systems of enterprises within the “Uztextileindustry” Association was approximately 3.1 out of 5, reflecting a stable foundation and significant opportunities for further development. The analysis demonstrated particularly strong prospects for enhancing the areas of information technology and monitoring, which can further improve the effectiveness and sustainability of internal control systems. In response to these findings, a comprehensive five-criterion evaluation methodology was developed, incorporating the specific characteristics of the textile industry, including organizational structure, policies and procedures, communication systems, information technologies, and monitoring.

The implementation of the five-criterion methodology across the industry is expected to create substantial socio-economic advantages. Strengthening internal control mechanisms and improving operational transparency will contribute to higher management efficiency, optimization of operational processes, and more effective resource utilization. As a result, the industry is expected to achieve considerable economic savings, while also increasing the reliability and attractiveness of enterprises for both domestic and foreign investors. It is anticipated that the investment potential of the sector may increase by approximately 18–25%, further supporting sustainable industrial growth.

In addition, the methodology will contribute to the professional development of human capital within the sector. The number of qualified internal auditors and corporate governance specialists is expected to increase to approximately 1,500–2,000 professionals, creating a stronger institutional environment and supporting the long-term modernization of management systems in textile enterprises.

Overall, the proposed methodology is expected to make a significant strategic contribution to enhancing the international competitiveness of the textile industry, strengthening corporate governance practices, and supporting the successful achievement of the goals outlined in the “Uzbekistan–2030 Strategy.”

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